

United Nations

**Financial Regulations and Rules
of the United Nations**

Secretary-General's bulletin

ST/SGB/2013/4
1 July 2013

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Financial Regulations and Rules

1. The Secretary-General hereby promulgates a revised edition of the Financial Regulations and Rules of the United Nations.
2. Through its Financial Regulations, the General Assembly issues the broad legislative directives governing the financial management of the United Nations. The revised Financial Regulations were approved by the Assembly in section IV of its resolution 67/246. In accordance with that resolution, the revised Financial Regulations shall take effect as from 1 July 2013, provided that, as a transitional measure, the regulations relating to the preparation and reporting of financial statements shall not be implemented for the regular budget, trust funds and reserves and special accounts, other than peacekeeping accounts, until 1 January 2014.
3. Within the framework of the Financial Regulations, as provided for in regulation 5.8, the Secretary-General formulates and promulgates the Financial Rules, which not only provide details to further define the parameters within which staff and the Administration must exercise their responsibilities, but also constitute a statement as to the manner in which the Financial Regulations are to be implemented. The revised Financial Rules shall take effect as from 1 July 2013, provided that, as a transitional measure, the rules relating to the preparation and reporting of financial statements shall not be implemented for the regular budget, trust funds and reserves and special accounts, other than peacekeeping accounts, until 1 January 2014.
4. A detailed explanation of the changes made in the Financial Regulations and Rules can be found in the report of the Secretary-General entitled "Proposed revisions to the Financial Regulations of the United Nations for the adoption of International Public Sector Accounting Standards" (A/67/345).
5. The present bulletin supersedes Secretary-General's bulletins ST/SGB/2003/7 of 9 May 2003 and ST/SGB/2003/7/Amend.1 of 16 December 2010.

(Signed) **BAN Ki-moon**
Secretary-General

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Article I

General provisions

Applicability and authority

Regulation 1.1. These Regulations shall govern the financial administration of the United Nations, including the International Court of Justice.

Rule 101.1

The Financial Rules are promulgated by the Secretary-General in accordance with the provisions of the Financial Regulations approved by the General Assembly. They shall govern all the financial management activities of the United Nations except as may otherwise explicitly be provided by the Assembly or unless specifically exempted therefrom by the Secretary-General. The Secretary-General hereby delegates authority and responsibility for the implementation of the Financial Regulations and Rules to the Under-Secretary-General for Management. The Under-Secretary-General for Management may in turn delegate, by administrative instruction, authority for specified aspects of the Financial Regulations and Rules. Such administrative instructions will state whether the delegated official may assign aspects of this authority to other officials. In the application of the Financial Regulations and Rules, officials shall be guided by the principles of effective and efficient financial management and the exercise of economy.

Responsibility and accountability

Rule 101.2

All United Nations staff are obligated to comply with the Financial Regulations and Rules and with administrative instructions issued in connection with those Regulations and Rules. Any staff member who contravenes the Financial Regulations and Rules or corresponding administrative instructions may be held personally accountable and financially liable for his or her actions.

Definitions

Rule 101.3

For the purpose of these Rules:

(a) “Advisory Committee” shall mean the Advisory Committee on Administrative and Budgetary Questions;

(b) “Department” shall mean any department, office or other distinct organizational entity;

(c) “Head of department” shall mean the Under-Secretary-General, Assistant Secretary-General, Director or other officer in charge of a department, as defined in subparagraph (b) above.

Financial period

Regulation 1.2. The financial period shall consist of a calendar year, except for peacekeeping operations with special accounts, for which the financial period shall be one year, from 1 July to 30 June.

Budget period

Regulation 1.3. The budget period for the proposed programme budget shall consist of two consecutive calendar years, the first of which shall be an even year, except for peacekeeping operations with special accounts, for which the budget period shall be one year, from 1 July to 30 June.

Effective date

Regulation 1.4. These Regulations shall become effective on 1 July 2013. They may be amended only by the General Assembly.

Article II Budgets

A. Programme budget

Authority and responsibility

Regulation 2.1. The proposed programme budget for each budget period shall be prepared by the Secretary-General.

Rule 102.1

(a) The Secretary-General shall decide on the programme content and resource allocation of the proposed programme budget to be submitted to the General Assembly.

(b) Heads of department shall prepare programme budget proposals for the forthcoming budget period at such times and in such detail as the Under-Secretary-General for Management may prescribe and in accordance with the Financial Regulations and Rules and the Regulations and Rules Governing Programme Planning, the Programme Aspects of the Budget, the Monitoring of Implementation and the Methods of Evaluation.

Presentation, content and methodology

Regulation 2.2. The proposed programme budget shall cover income and expenditures for the budget period to which it relates and shall be presented in United States dollars.

Regulation 2.3. The proposed programme budget shall be divided into parts, sections and programmes. Programme narratives shall set out subprogrammes,

outputs, objectives and accomplishments expected during the biennium. The proposed programme budget shall be preceded by a statement explaining the main changes made in the content of the programme and the volume of resources allocated to it in relation to the previous biennium. The proposed programme budget shall be accompanied by such information, annexes and explanatory statements as may be requested by or on behalf of the General Assembly and such further annexes or statements as the Secretary-General may deem necessary and useful.

Rule 102.2

In addition to the detailed requirements of the Regulations and Rules Governing Programme Planning, the Programme Aspects of the Budget, the Monitoring of Implementation and the Methods of Evaluation, the proposed programme budget shall contain:

(a) A detailed statement of resources by section, programme and subprogramme; for purposes of comparison, the expenditures for the previous budget period and the revised appropriations for the current budget period shall be indicated alongside the resource estimates for the forthcoming budget period;

(b) A statement of estimated income, including staff assessment income and net income in accordance with regulation 3.3; information on revenue-producing activities shall show estimated gross revenue and expenditure for each activity as well as the credit to the income section of the budget in respect of the net revenue from each such activity.

Review and approval

Regulation 2.4. The Secretary-General shall, in the second year of a budget period, submit his or her proposed programme budget for the following budget period to the General Assembly at its regular session. This proposed programme budget shall be transmitted to all Member States at least five weeks prior to the opening of that session.

Regulation 2.5. The Secretary-General shall, at least 12 weeks prior to the opening of the regular session of the General Assembly in the second year of a budget period, submit his or her proposed programme budget for the following budget period to the Advisory Committee for examination.

Regulation 2.6. The Advisory Committee shall prepare a report to the General Assembly on the programme budget proposed by the Secretary-General. This report shall be transmitted to all Member States at the same time as the proposed programme budget. The report, or an addendum to it, shall contain the recommendations of the Advisory Committee concerning the statement of the Secretary-General on the programme budget implications of the recommendations of the Committee for Programme and Coordination.

Regulation 2.7. The General Assembly shall, in the second year of a budget period, adopt the programme budget for the following budget period after consideration of the proposed programme budget and the report of the Advisory Committee thereon by the Administrative and Budgetary Committee of the Assembly.

Publication of the approved programme budget

Rule 102.3

The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall arrange for the publication of the programme budget as approved by the General Assembly.

Revised and supplementary programme budget requirements

Regulation 2.8. Supplementary programme budget proposals may be submitted by the Secretary-General whenever necessary.

Rule 102.4

Revised and supplementary programme budget proposals may be submitted in the following instances:

- (a) When, in the interest of peace and security, urgent approval is required;
- (b) When they include activities which the Secretary-General considers to be of the highest urgency and which could not have been foreseen at the time the initial programme budget proposals were prepared;
- (c) In respect of decisions taken by the General Assembly;
- (d) In respect of decisions taken by the Security Council, the Economic and Social Council or the Trusteeship Council;
- (e) When they cover activities mentioned in earlier programme budget proposals as items for which later submissions would be made;
- (f) When they involve changes in expenditure requirements associated with inflation and currency fluctuations.

Revised and supplementary programme budget proposals, presentation and submission

Regulation 2.9. The Secretary-General shall prepare supplementary programme budget proposals in a form consistent with the approved programme budget and shall submit such proposals to the General Assembly. The Advisory Committee shall review the supplementary proposals and report thereon.

Rule 102.5

(a) Heads of department shall prepare revised and supplementary programme budget proposals in such detail and at such times as the Under-Secretary-General for Management may prescribe.

(b) The Secretary-General shall decide on the programme content and resource allocation of all revised and supplementary programme budget proposals to be submitted to the General Assembly.

Resolutions with programme budget implications

Regulation 2.10. No council, commission or other competent body shall take a decision involving either a change in the programme budget approved by the General Assembly or the possible requirement of expenditure unless it has received and taken account of a report of the Secretary-General on the programme budget implications of the proposal.

Regulation 2.11. Where, in the opinion of the Secretary-General, a proposed expenditure cannot be made from existing appropriation, it shall not be incurred until the General Assembly has made the necessary appropriation unless the Secretary-General certifies that the expenditure can be made under the provisions of the Assembly resolution relating to unforeseen and extraordinary expenses.

Rule 102.6

All heads of department are responsible for preparing, obtaining clearance thereon from the Under-Secretary-General for Management, and presenting to relevant legislative bodies the statements on programme budget implications required by regulation 2.10.

Unforeseen and extraordinary expenses

Rule 102.7

(a) Authorizations to incur commitments in accordance with General Assembly resolutions relating to unforeseen and extraordinary expenses shall be issued by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall report to the General Assembly on the status of all commitments relating to unforeseen and extraordinary expenses in the performance reports on the programme budget.

B. Peacekeeping operation budgets

Authority, responsibility, submission and approval

Regulation 2.12. Budgets for peacekeeping operations setting out objectives, expected accomplishments and outputs shall be prepared by the Secretary-General for consideration and approval by the General Assembly.

Regulation 2.13. The Secretary-General shall submit twice a year to the General Assembly for informational purposes a table summarizing the budgetary requirements of each peacekeeping operation for the budget period from 1 July to 30 June, including a breakdown of expenditure by major line item and the aggregate total resource requirement.

Rule 102.8

(a) The Secretary-General shall decide on the objectives, expected accomplishments, outputs, activities and resource allocation in all peacekeeping operation budgets submitted to the General Assembly.

(b) Budget estimates for peacekeeping operations shall be prepared at such times and in such detail and form as the Under-Secretary-General for Management may prescribe and in accordance with the requirements of the General Assembly.

C. International Court of Justice

Budget preparation and submission

Regulation 2.14. The programme budget proposals of the International Court of Justice shall be prepared by the Court in consultation with the Secretary-General. The programme budget proposals shall be submitted to the General Assembly by the Secretary-General, together with such observations as he or she may deem desirable.

Article III Contributions and other income

A. Programme budget

Assessed contributions

Regulation 3.1. Appropriations, subject to the adjustments effected in accordance with the provisions of regulation 3.2, shall be financed by contributions from Member States, according to the scale of assessments determined by the General Assembly. Pending the receipt of such contributions, the appropriations may be financed from the Working Capital Fund.

Regulation 3.2. For each of the two years of a budget period, the contributions of Member States shall be assessed on the basis of half of the appropriations approved by the General Assembly for that budget period, except that adjustments shall be made to the assessments in respect of:

(a) Supplementary appropriations for which contributions have not previously been assessed on Member States;

(b) Half of the estimated amounts under the categories of revenue defined in regulation 3.3 for the budget period for which credits have not previously been taken into account and any adjustments in estimated amounts under these categories of revenue previously taken into account;

(c) Contributions resulting from the assessment of new Member States under the provisions of regulation 3.8;

(d) Any balance of the appropriations surrendered under regulations 5.3 and 5.4;

(e) Half of the Member States' credits in the Tax Equalization Fund for the budget period estimated to be not required to meet charges for tax refunds during the calendar year and any adjustments in the estimated credits previously taken into account.

Regulation 3.3. Member States' assessments shall be offset in accordance with regulation 3.2 by net revenue from the following revenue categories:

- (a) Revenue-producing activities;
- (b) Investment revenue;
- (c) Services rendered;
- (d) Contributions from new Member States in accordance with regulation 3.8 and non-member States in accordance with regulation 3.9;
- (e) Other/miscellaneous revenue, including revenue from rental of office premises, and unspecified contributions in accordance with regulation 3.14;
- (f) Any other revenue attributable to Member States.

Requests for payment of assessed contributions

Regulation 3.4. After the General Assembly has adopted or revised the programme budget and determined the amount of the Working Capital Fund, the Secretary-General shall:

- (a) Transmit the relevant documents to Member States;
- (b) Inform them of their commitments in respect of annual contributions and advances to the Working Capital Fund;
- (c) Request them to remit their contributions and advances.

Rule 103.1

The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall comply with regulation 3.4 within 30 days of the General Assembly's decision to approve or revise the programme budget and the level of the Working Capital Fund. Requests for the payment of assessed contributions and advances to the Working Capital Fund shall also inform Member States of the extent to which and the conditions under which their contributions and advances may be paid in currencies other than the United States dollar.

Payment of assessed contributions

Regulation 3.5. Contributions and advances shall be considered as due and payable in full within 30 days of the receipt of the communication of the Secretary-General referred to in regulation 3.4 or on the first day of the calendar year to which they relate, whichever is later. As of 1 January of the following calendar year, the unpaid balance of such contributions and advances shall be considered to be one year in arrears.

Regulation 3.6. Payments made by a Member State shall be credited first to the Working Capital Fund and then to the contributions due in the order in which the Member State was assessed.

Regulation 3.7. The Secretary-General shall submit to the General Assembly at each regular session a report on the collection of contributions and advances to the Working Capital Fund.

Assessed contributions from new Member States

Regulation 3.8. New Member States shall be required to make a contribution for the year in which they become Member States and to provide their proportion of the total advances to the Working Capital Fund at rates to be determined by the General Assembly.

Assessed contributions from non-member States

Regulation 3.9. States which are not Members of the United Nations but which become parties to the Statute of the International Court of Justice or treaty bodies financed from United Nations appropriations shall contribute to the expenses of such bodies at rates to be determined by the General Assembly. States which are not Members of the United Nations but which participate in organs or conferences financed from United Nations appropriations shall contribute to the expenses of such organs or conferences at rates to be determined by the General Assembly, unless the Assembly decides with respect to any such State to exempt it from the requirement of so contributing. Such contributions shall be treated in accordance with regulation 3.3.

Rule 103.2

At the beginning of each calendar year, the Under-Secretary-General for Management shall determine the assessment base on which non-member States are called upon to make contributions, calculate the required contribution of each non-member State applying criteria approved by the General Assembly and inform each non-member State accordingly.

Currency of assessed contributions

Regulation 3.10. Annual contributions and advances to the Working Capital Fund shall be assessed and paid in United States dollars.

Rule 103.3

(a) To the extent authorized by the General Assembly, and notwithstanding regulation 3.10, assessed contributions and advances to the Working Capital Fund may be paid in currencies other than the United States dollar if the Under-Secretary-General for Management is satisfied that:

(i) The currencies are required to meet expenses to be settled in the same currencies;

(ii) The currencies represent freely transferable and readily usable funds throughout the country within which they are to be used, or the donor country, if different, without the need for further negotiations with regard to exchange or other regulations or controls.

(b) The equivalent, in United States dollars, of contributions paid in other currencies is calculated at the most favourable rate of exchange available to the United Nations on the date of payment (normally the market buying rate).

B. Peacekeeping operation budgets

Assessed contributions

Regulation 3.11. Except as otherwise specified by the General Assembly, the appropriations for peacekeeping operations shall be financed by contributions from Member States according to the scale of assessments approved by the Assembly, as modified by any related system of adjustments approved by the Assembly. The payment of assessed contributions for peacekeeping operations shall also be governed by regulation 3.5. Contributions and advances for peacekeeping operations shall be assessed and paid in United States dollars.

C. Voluntary contributions, gifts and donations

Acceptance and purpose

Regulation 3.12. Voluntary contributions, whether or not in cash, may be accepted by the Secretary-General provided that the purposes for which the contributions are made are consistent with the policies, aims and activities of the Organization and provided further that the acceptance of voluntary contributions that directly or indirectly involve additional financial liability for the Organization shall require the consent of the appropriate authority.

Regulation 3.13. Moneys accepted for purposes specified by the donor shall be treated as trust funds or special accounts under regulations 4.13 and 4.14.

Authority and liability

Rule 103.4

(a) In cases other than those approved by the General Assembly, the receipt of any voluntary contribution, gift or donation to be administered by the United Nations requires the approval of the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) Voluntary contributions, gifts or donations that directly or indirectly involve additional financial liability for the Organization may be accepted only with the approval of the General Assembly.

(c) Gifts or donations are to be defined and administered as voluntary contributions.

D. Revenue

Voluntary contributions, gifts and donations

Regulation 3.14. Moneys accepted in respect of which no purpose is specified shall be treated as other/miscellaneous revenue.

Reimbursements of expenditures

Rule 103.5

Within the same budget period, reimbursements of actual expenditures incurred may be credited to the accounts against which they were originally charged; reimbursements of actual expenditures incurred in prior budget periods shall be credited as other/miscellaneous revenue in accordance with regulation 3.3.

E. Receipt of funds

Receipt and deposit

Rule 103.6

(a) The United Nations shall receive moneys, issue official receipts and deposit moneys in an official bank account on a timely basis for the recording in the accounts in accordance with the procedures established by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) If officials other than those designated by the Under-Secretary-General receive money intended for the United Nations, they must promptly convey this money to an official authorized to issue an official receipt.

Article IV Custody of funds

A. Internal accounts

General Fund

Regulation 4.1. There shall be established a general fund for the purpose of accounting for the programme budget undertakings of the Organization. The contributions paid by Member States under regulation 3.1, the revenue categories under regulation 3.3 and any advances made from the Working Capital Fund shall be available to fund expenditure of the General Fund.

Working Capital Fund

Regulation 4.2. There shall be established a working capital fund in an amount and for purposes to be determined from time to time by the General Assembly.

The source of moneys of the Working Capital Fund shall be advances from Member States, and those advances, made in accordance with the scale of assessments as determined by the Assembly for the apportionment of the expenses of the United Nations, shall be carried to the credit of Member States that have made such advances.

Advances from the Working Capital Fund

Regulation 4.3. Advances made from the Working Capital Fund to finance budgetary appropriations shall be reimbursed to the Fund as soon as receipts from contributions are available for that purpose.

Regulation 4.4. Except when such advances are recoverable from some other source, advances made from the Working Capital Fund for unforeseen and extraordinary expenses or other authorized purposes shall be reimbursed through the submission of supplementary programme budget proposals.

Rule 104.1

Advances from the Working Capital Fund may be made only for the purposes and within the terms and conditions prescribed by the General Assembly and only with the approval of the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

Peacekeeping Reserve Fund

Regulation 4.5. There shall be established a peacekeeping reserve fund as a cash flow mechanism to ensure the rapid response of the Organization during the start-up phase of new peacekeeping operations and the expansion of existing peacekeeping operations and to meet unforeseen and extraordinary expenses and capital requirements (outlays) related to peacekeeping. The level of the fund and the means by which it shall be financed by Member States shall be determined by the General Assembly.

Advances from the Peacekeeping Reserve Fund

Regulation 4.6. If a decision of the Security Council relating to the start-up or expansion phase of peacekeeping operations results in the need to meet expenses and capital requirements, the Secretary-General is authorized, with the prior concurrence of the Advisory Committee and subject to regulation 4.8, to enter into commitments not to exceed the balance of the Peacekeeping Reserve Fund, and not to exceed \$100 million per decision of the Security Council. The cumulative total of outstanding commitment authority in respect of the start-up or expansion phase of peacekeeping operations is not to exceed the total level of the Peacekeeping Reserve Fund at any one time; however, the appropriation by the General Assembly of any outstanding commitments shall automatically restore this commitment authority to the extent of the amount appropriated.

Regulation 4.7. Advances made from the Peacekeeping Reserve Fund shall be reimbursed as soon as receipts from contributions are available for those purposes.

Regulation 4.8. If a decision of the Security Council results in the need for the Secretary-General to enter into commitments for the start-up or expansion phase of peacekeeping operations in an amount exceeding \$100 million per decision of the Security Council or exceeding the total level of the Peacekeeping Reserve Fund, the matter shall be brought to the General Assembly as soon as possible for a decision on commitment authority and assessment.

Regulation 4.9. The Secretary-General and the Advisory Committee shall report to the General Assembly on any exercise of a commitment authority given under regulation 4.6, together with the circumstances relating thereto, in the context of the next report submitted to the Assembly on the financing of the relevant peacekeeping operation.

Rule 104.2

Advances from the Peacekeeping Reserve Fund may be made only for the purposes and within the terms and conditions prescribed, as appropriate, by the Security Council, the General Assembly and the Advisory Committee and only with the approval of the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

Tax Equalization Fund

Regulation 4.10. There shall be established a tax equalization fund to which the staff assessment deductions from those staff salaries financed from assessed contributions shall be credited. Within the Tax Equalization Fund, revenue shall be recorded as credits to Member States and divided among them in accordance with the proportions approved by the General Assembly for the relevant rates of assessment. All credits shall pertain to a specific year and shall be calculated in accordance with the rates of assessment approved for that same year; prior-period adjustments shall also observe this principle.

Use of the Tax Equalization Fund

Regulation 4.11. Tax Equalization Fund revenue shall be used to refund staff members for income taxes levied by Member States in respect of their United Nations remuneration. Commitments shall be established against the Tax Equalization Fund to cover the estimated liabilities in respect of the refunds made to staff members of those income taxes. If a Member State's credit in the Tax Equalization Fund is insufficient for this purpose, the shortfall shall be added to and recovered from assessed contributions due from that Member State in the subsequent financial period. Where income tax is levied on staff financed from sources of funds that do not contribute to the Tax Equalization Fund, the additional costs for tax reimbursement shall be borne by those sources of funds.

Regulation 4.12. In accordance with regulation 3.2, any balance on a Member State's tax equalization account after the commitments referred to in regulation

4.11 have been satisfied shall be credited against the assessed contributions due from that Member State the following year.

Trust funds and reserve and special accounts

Regulation 4.13. Trust funds and reserve and special accounts may be established by the Secretary-General and shall be reported to the Advisory Committee.

Regulation 4.14. The purpose and limits of each trust fund and reserve and special account shall be clearly defined by the appropriate authority. Unless otherwise provided by the General Assembly, such funds and accounts shall be administered in accordance with the present Regulations.

Rule 104.3

Trust funds and reserve and special accounts may be established by the General Assembly or the Secretary-General in respect of specific activities entrusted to the Organization. The establishment, purpose and limits of trust funds and reserve and special accounts established under the authority of the Secretary-General require the approval of the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

B. Banking

Bank accounts, authority and policy

Regulation 4.15. The Secretary-General shall designate the bank or banks in which the funds of the Organization shall be kept.

Rule 104.4

The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall designate the banks in which the funds of the United Nations shall be kept, shall establish all official bank accounts required for the transaction of United Nations business and shall designate those officials to whom signatory authority is delegated for the operation of those accounts. The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall also authorize all bank account closures. United Nations bank accounts are to be opened and operated in accordance with the following guidelines:

(a) Bank accounts shall be designated “official accounts of the United Nations” and the relevant authority shall be notified that those accounts are exempt from all taxation;

(b) Banks shall be required to provide prompt statements;

(c) Two signatures, or their electronic equivalent, shall be required on all cheques and other withdrawal instructions, including electronic modes of payment;

(d) All banks shall be required to recognize that the Under-Secretary-General for Management is authorized to receive, upon request or as promptly as is practicable, all information pertaining to official bank accounts of the United Nations.

Bank signatories

Rule 104.5

Bank signatory authority and responsibility is assigned on a personal basis and cannot be delegated. Bank signatories cannot exercise the approving functions assigned in accordance with rule 105.6. Designated bank signatories must:

(a) Ensure that there are sufficient funds in the bank account when cheques and other payment instructions are presented for payment;

(b) Verify that all cheques and other payment instructions are made to the order of the named payee approved by an approving officer (designated in accordance with rule 105.6) and prepared in accordance with banking laws, regulations and standards;

(c) Ensure that cheques and other banking instruments are properly safeguarded and that when they are obsolete they are destroyed in accordance with rule 106.8.

Exchange of currencies

Rule 104.6

Officials responsible for the operation of United Nations bank accounts or for holding United Nations cash or negotiable instruments are not authorized to exchange one currency for another, except to the minimum extent necessary for the transaction of official business and for currency management.

Remittances to offices away from Headquarters

Rule 104.7

Offices away from Headquarters shall obtain their funds through remittances from Headquarters, as required. In the absence of a special authorization from the Under-Secretary-General for Management, those remittances shall not exceed the amount required to bring cash balances up to the levels necessary to meet the recipient office's estimated cash requirements for the next month.

Cash advances

Rule 104.8

(a) Petty cash advances and Cashier's Fund advances may be made only by and to officials designated for this purpose by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) The relevant accounts shall be maintained on an imprest system and the amount and purpose of each advance shall be defined by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(c) The Under-Secretary-General for Management may approve other cash advances as may be permitted by the Staff Regulations and Rules and administrative instructions and as may otherwise be authorized in writing by him or her.

(d) A payee's written receipt shall be obtained for all disbursements of cash advances.

Rule 104.9

Officials to whom cash advances are issued shall be held personally accountable and financially liable for the proper management and safekeeping of cash so advanced and must be in a position to account for these advances at all times. They shall submit monthly accounts unless otherwise directed by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

Disbursements/payments

Rule 104.10

(a) All disbursements shall be made by electronic funds transfer, by wire transfer or by cheque except to the extent that cash disbursements are authorized by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) Disbursements shall be recorded in the accounts as at the date on which they are made.

Reconciliation of bank accounts

Rule 104.11

Every month, unless an exception is authorized by the Under-Secretary-General for Management, all financial transactions, including bank charges and commissions, must be reconciled with the information submitted by banks in accordance with rule 104.4. This reconciliation must be performed by an official playing no actual part in the receipt or disbursement of funds; if the staffing of an outposted office makes this impracticable, alternative arrangements may be established in consultation with the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

C. Investments

Authority, responsibility and policy

Regulation 4.16. The Secretary-General may make investments of moneys of the Organization not needed for immediate requirements, having regard to the particular requirements as to the liquidity of funds.

Rule 104.12

(a) The authority to make and prudently manage investments under regulation 4.16 is delegated to the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall ensure, including by establishing appropriate guidelines, that funds are invested in such a way as to place primary emphasis on minimizing the risk to principal funds while ensuring the liquidity necessary to meet the Organization's cash-flow requirements. In addition to these criteria, investments shall be selected on the basis of achieving the highest reasonable rate of return and shall accord with the principles of the United Nations.

Rule 104.13

Records of all investments shall be maintained showing all the relevant details for each investment, including face value, cost, date of maturity, place of deposit, proceeds of sale and revenue earned.

Rule 104.14

(a) All investments shall be made through and maintained by recognized financial institutions designated by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) All investment transactions, including the withdrawal of invested resources, require the authorization and signature of two officials designated for that purpose by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

Revenue

Regulation 4.17. Revenue derived from investments shall be credited as provided in the rules relating to each fund or account.

Regulation 4.18. Revenue derived from investments of the Working Capital Fund shall be credited as investment revenue of the General Fund.

Rule 104.15

(a) Revenue from General Fund investments shall be credited to it as investment revenue.

(b) Revenue from investments pertaining to trust funds and special accounts shall be credited to the trust fund or special account concerned.

Losses

Rule 104.16

(a) Any investment losses must be accounted for and reported in accordance with policies established by the Under-Secretary-General for Management and the International Public Sector Accounting Standards.

(b) Investment losses shall be borne by the fund, trust fund, reserve or special account from which the principal amounts were obtained.

Article V

Utilization of funds

A. Appropriations

Authorization

Regulation 5.1. The appropriations voted by the General Assembly shall constitute an authorization to the Secretary-General to incur commitments and make payments for the purposes for which the appropriations were voted and up to the amounts so voted.

Available period

Regulation 5.2. Appropriations shall be available for commitment during the budget period to which they relate.

Regulation 5.3. Appropriations shall remain available for 12 months following the end of the budget period to which they relate to the extent that they are required to discharge commitments in respect of goods supplied and services rendered in the budget period and to liquidate any other outstanding legal obligation of the budget period. The balance of the appropriations shall be surrendered.

Regulation 5.4. At the end of the 12-month period provided in regulation 5.3 above, the then remaining balance of any appropriations retained will be surrendered. Where a commitment remains valid at the end of the 12-month period, it shall be cancelled and funded from the current appropriations.

Regulation 5.5. Appropriations required in respect of commitments to Governments for troops, formed police units, logistical support and other goods supplied and services rendered to peacekeeping operations shall be retained beyond the 12-month period provided for in regulation 5.3 if the requisite claims are not received or processed during the period to which the appropriations relate. Those appropriations shall remain valid for an additional period of four years following the end of the 12-month period provided in regulation 5.3. At the end of the additional four-year period the remaining balance of any appropriations retained will be surrendered. Where a commitment remains valid at the end of the additional four years it shall be cancelled and funded from current appropriations.

Transfers between appropriations

Regulation 5.6. No transfer between appropriation sections may be made without authorization by the General Assembly.

Rule 105.1

The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall obtain the approval of the Advisory Committee in order to transfer credits between programme budget

appropriations in those instances where the General Assembly has delegated its authority under regulation 5.6 to the Committee.

Commitments against appropriations for future budget periods

Regulation 5.7. The Secretary-General may enter into commitments for future budget periods, provided that such commitments:

(a) Are for activities which have been approved by the General Assembly and are expected to continue beyond the end of the current budget period; or

(b) Are authorized by specific decisions of the Assembly.

Rule 105.2

In accordance with regulation 5.7, the authority to approve commitments against future budget periods is delegated to the Under-Secretary-General for Management. The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall disclose the commitments against future budget periods in a note to the financial statements in accordance with the International Public Sector Accounting Standards. Such commitments shall constitute the first charges against relevant appropriations once they are approved by the General Assembly.

Administration of appropriations

Regulation 5.8. The Secretary-General shall:

(a) Establish detailed financial rules and procedures in order to ensure effective and efficient financial management and the exercise of economy;

(b) Cause all payments to be made on the basis of supporting documents which ensure that the services or goods have been received;

(c) Designate the officers who may receive money or assets, enter into commitments and make disbursements on behalf of the Organization;

(d) Maintain a system of internal controls designed to provide reasonable assurance regarding the reliability of financial reporting and assurance that the Organization's resources and assets are safeguarded in accordance with the regulatory framework, in order to meet the aims and objectives of the Organization.

B. Commitments and expenses

Authority and responsibility

Regulation 5.9. Commitments for current or future budget periods shall be incurred only after allotments or other appropriate authorizations have been issued under the authority of the Secretary-General.

Rule 105.3

The utilization of all funds requires the prior authorization of the Under-Secretary-General for Management. Such authorization may take the form of:

- (a) An allotment of funds or other authorization to incur commitments and expend specified funds for specified purposes during a specified period;
- (b) An authorization to employ staff against an approved staffing table.

Checks and balances**Rule 105.4**

Notwithstanding bank signatory functions assigned in accordance with rule 104.5, all commitments, disbursements and expenses require at least two authorizing signatures, in either conventional or electronic form. All commitments, disbursements and expenses must first be signed (“certified”) by a duly designated certifying officer (rule 105.5). Following certification, duly designated approving officers (rule 105.6) must then sign to “approve” the establishment of commitments, expenses and disbursements. Expenses recorded against an established, certified commitment do not require additional certification, provided that they do not exceed the amount committed by more than 10 per cent or \$4,000 (or its equivalent in other currencies), whichever is lower (rule 105.7). Expenses under \$4,000 (or its equivalent in other currencies) for which the recording of a commitment is unnecessary require both certification and approval.

Certifying officers**Rule 105.5**

(a) One or more officials shall be designated by the Under-Secretary-General for Management as the certifying officer(s) for the account(s) pertaining to a section or subsection of an approved budget. Certifying authority and responsibility is assigned on a personal basis and cannot be delegated. A certifying officer cannot exercise the approving functions assigned in accordance with rule 105.6.

(b) Certifying officers are responsible for managing the utilization of resources, including posts, in accordance with the purposes for which those resources were approved, the principles of efficiency and effectiveness, and the Financial Regulations and Rules of the United Nations. Certifying officers must maintain detailed records of all commitments, disbursements and expenses against the accounts for which they have been delegated responsibility. They must be prepared to submit any supporting documents, explanations and justifications requested by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(c) In cases where the goods/services received and the invoice received are consistent with the details of the commitment, the certification may be deemed to have taken place at commitment.

Approving officers

Rule 105.6

(a) Approving officers are designated by the Under-Secretary-General for Management to approve the entry into the accounts of commitments, disbursements and expenses relating to contracts, agreements, purchase orders and other forms of undertaking after verifying that they are in order and have been certified by a duly designated certifying officer. Approving officers are also responsible for approving the making of payments once they have ensured that they are properly due, confirming that the necessary goods and services have been received in accordance with the contract, agreement, purchase order or other form of undertaking by which they were ordered and, if the cost exceeds \$4,000 (or its equivalent in other currencies), in accordance with the purpose for which the relevant financial commitment was established. Approving officers must maintain detailed records and must be prepared to submit any supporting documents, explanations and justifications requested by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) Approving authority and responsibility is assigned on a personal basis and cannot be delegated. An approving officer cannot exercise the certifying functions assigned in accordance with rule 105.5 or the bank signatory functions assigned in accordance with rule 104.5.

(c) In cases where the goods/services received and the invoice received are consistent with the details of the commitment, the approval may be deemed to have taken place at commitment.

Establishment and revision of commitments

Rule 105.7

(a) Apart from the employment of staff against an authorized staffing table and consequential commitments under the Staff Regulations and Rules and allocations made to executing agencies, no undertaking, including by contract, agreement or purchase order, for an amount exceeding \$4,000 (or its equivalent in other currencies) shall be entered into until the appropriate credit(s) has (have) been reserved in the accounts by the certifying officer. This shall be done through the recording of commitments against which relevant payments or disbursements may be made. A commitment shall remain open until such point as it is liquidated, cancelled or recommitted in accordance with regulations 5.4 and 5.5, as appropriate.

(b) If, in the time that elapses between the establishment of a commitment and the processing of final payment, the cost of the relevant goods or services has, for whatever reason, increased by less than \$4,000 (or its equivalent in other currencies) or 10 per cent of the commitment, whichever is lower, no change need be made to the amount of the original commitment. If, however, the increase in costs exceeds \$4,000 (or its equivalent in other currencies), the original commitment must be revised to reflect this increase in requirements and further certification is required. All increases in commitments shall be subject to the same procedures as apply to the incurring of original commitments.

Review, recommitment and cancellation of commitments

Rule 105.8

(a) Outstanding commitments must be reviewed periodically by the responsible certifying officer(s). If a commitment is determined to be valid but cannot be liquidated during the period set forth in regulation 5.3, the provisions of regulations 5.4 and 5.5 shall, as appropriate, be applied. Commitments that are no longer valid shall be cancelled from the accounts forthwith and the resulting credit surrendered.

(b) When any commitment previously recorded in the accounts is, for any reason, reduced (other than by payment) or cancelled, the certifying officer shall accordingly ensure that appropriate adjustments are recorded in the accounts.

Commitment documents

Rule 105.9

A commitment must be based on a formal contract, agreement, purchase order or other form of undertaking, or on a liability recognized by the United Nations. All commitments must be supported by an appropriate commitment document.

Peacekeeping reimbursements

Regulation 5.10. Member States that contribute troops and formed police to peacekeeping operations shall be reimbursed at rates approved by the General Assembly. Member States shall also be reimbursed for contingent-owned equipment at rates approved by the Assembly.

Rule 105.10

The payment of reimbursements to Member States, based upon rates and peacekeeping operation budgets approved by the General Assembly, may be made only with the approval of the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

Management services agreements

Rule 105.11

(a) Management and other support services may be provided to Governments, specialized agencies and other international and intergovernmental organizations or in support of activities financed from trust funds or special accounts on a reimbursable, reciprocal or other basis consistent with the policies, aims and activities of the United Nations, with the approval of the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

(b) Each management and support services arrangement shall be covered by a written agreement between the United Nations and the entity on whose behalf the services are to be provided. Such agreements shall, inter alia, specify the services which the United Nations is to provide in return for full reimbursement to the United Nations of any costs incurred by it in providing those services.

Ex gratia payments

Regulation 5.11. The Secretary-General may make such ex gratia payments as are deemed to be necessary in the interest of the Organization, provided that a statement of such payments shall be submitted to the Board of Auditors with the financial statements.

Rule 105.12

Ex gratia payments may be made in cases where, although in the opinion of the Legal Counsel there is no clear legal liability on the part of the United Nations, payment is in the interest of the Organization. A summary statement of all ex gratia payments shall be provided to the Board of Auditors not later than three months following the end of the financial period. The approval of the Under-Secretary-General for Management is required for all ex gratia payments.

C. Procurement

General principles

Regulation 5.12. Procurement functions include all actions necessary for the acquisition, by purchase or lease, of property, including products and real property, and of services, including works. The following general principles shall be given due consideration when exercising the procurement functions of the United Nations:

- (a) **Best value for money;**
- (b) **Fairness, integrity and transparency;**
- (c) **Effective international competition;**
- (d) **The interest of the United Nations.**

Regulation 5.13. Tenders for goods and services shall be invited by advertisement, except where the Secretary-General deems that, in the interests of the Organization, a departure from this regulation is desirable.

Authority and responsibility

Rule 105.13

(a) The Under-Secretary-General for Management is responsible for the procurement functions of the United Nations, shall establish all United Nations procurement systems and shall designate the officials responsible for performing procurement functions.

(b) The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall establish review committees, at Headquarters and other locations, to render written advice to the Under-Secretary-General for Management on procurement actions leading to the award or amendment of procurement contracts, which, for purposes of these Regulations and Rules, includes agreements or other written instruments such as purchase orders and contracts that involve income to the United Nations. The

Under-Secretary-General for Management shall establish the composition and the terms of reference of such committees, which shall include the types and monetary values of proposed procurement actions subject to review.

(c) Where the advice of a review committee is required, no final action leading to the award or amendment of a procurement contract may be taken before such advice is received. In cases where the Under-Secretary-General for Management decides not to accept the advice of such a review committee, he or she shall record in writing the reasons for that decision.

Competition

Rule 105.14

Consistent with the principles set out in regulation 5.12 and except as otherwise provided in rule 105.16, procurement contracts shall be awarded on the basis of effective competition, and to this end the competitive process shall, as necessary, include:

(a) Acquisition planning for developing an overall procurement strategy and procurement methodologies;

(b) Market research for identifying potential suppliers;

(c) Consideration of prudent commercial practices;

(d) Formal methods of solicitation, utilizing invitations to bid or requests for proposals on the basis of advertisement or direct solicitation of invited suppliers, or informal methods of solicitation, such as requests for quotations. The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall issue administrative instructions concerning the types of procurement activities and monetary values for which such methods of solicitation are to be used. Such formal and informal methods of solicitation may be conducted by means of electronic data interchange, provided the Under-Secretary-General for Management has ensured that the electronic data interchange system is capable of ensuring authentication and confidentiality of the information transmitted;

(e) Public bid openings; for purposes of bidding by means of electronic data interchange, the virtual opening of bids is considered public.

Formal methods of solicitation

Rule 105.15

(a) When a formal invitation to bid has been issued, the procurement contract shall be awarded to the qualified bidder whose bid substantially conforms to the requirements set forth in the solicitation documents and is evaluated to be the one with the lowest cost to the United Nations.

(b) When a formal request for proposals has been issued, the procurement contract shall be awarded to the qualified proposer whose proposal, all factors considered, is the most responsive to the requirements set forth in the solicitation documents.

(c) The Under-Secretary-General for Management may, in the interest of the United Nations, reject bids or proposals for a particular procurement action, recording the reasons for rejection in writing. The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall then determine whether to undertake a new solicitation, to directly negotiate a procurement contract pursuant to rule 105.16 or to terminate or suspend the procurement action.

Exceptions to the use of formal methods of solicitation

Rule 105.16

(a) The Under-Secretary-General for Management may determine for a particular procurement action that using formal methods of solicitation is not in the best interest of the United Nations:

(i) When there is no competitive marketplace for the requirement, such as where a monopoly exists, where prices are fixed by legislation or government regulation or where the requirement involves a proprietary product or service;

(ii) When there has been a previous determination or there is a need to standardize the requirement;

(iii) When the proposed procurement contract is the result of cooperation with other organizations of the United Nations system, pursuant to rule 105.17;

(iv) When offers for identical products and services have been obtained competitively within a reasonable period and the prices and conditions offered remain competitive;

(v) When, within a reasonable prior period, a formal solicitation has not produced satisfactory results;

(vi) When the proposed procurement contract is for the purchase or lease of real property and market conditions do not allow for effective competition;

(vii) When there is an exigency for the requirement;

(viii) When the proposed procurement contract relates to obtaining services that cannot be evaluated objectively;

(ix) When the Under-Secretary-General for Management otherwise determines that a formal solicitation will not give satisfactory results;

(x) When the value of the procurement is below the monetary threshold established for formal methods of solicitation.

(b) When a determination is made pursuant to paragraph (a) above, the Under-Secretary-General for Management shall record the reasons in writing and may then award a procurement contract, either on the basis of an informal method of solicitation or on the basis of a directly negotiated contract, to a qualified vendor whose offer substantially conforms to the requirement at an acceptable price.

Cooperation

Rule 105.17

(a) The Under-Secretary-General for Management may cooperate with other organizations of the United Nations system to meet the procurement requirements of the United Nations, provided that the regulations and rules of those organizations are consistent with those of the United Nations. The Under-Secretary-General for Management may, as appropriate, enter into agreements for such purposes. Such cooperation may include carrying out common procurement actions together or the United Nations entering into a contract relying on a procurement decision of another United Nations organization or requesting another United Nations organization to carry out procurement activities on behalf of the United Nations.

(b) The Under-Secretary-General for Management may, to the extent authorized by the General Assembly, cooperate with a Government, non-governmental organization or other public international organization in respect of procurement activities and, as appropriate, enter into agreements for such purposes.

Written contracts

Rule 105.18

(a) Written procurement contracts shall be used to formalize every procurement action with a monetary value exceeding specific thresholds established by the Under-Secretary-General for Management. Such arrangements shall, as appropriate, specify in detail:

- (i) The nature of the products or services being procured;
- (ii) The quantity being procured;
- (iii) The contract or unit price;
- (iv) The period covered;
- (v) Conditions to be fulfilled, including the United Nations general conditions of contract and implications for non-delivery;
- (vi) Terms of delivery and payment;
- (vii) Name and address of the supplier.

(b) The requirement for written procurement contracts shall not be interpreted to restrict the use of any electronic means of data interchange. Before any electronic means of data interchange is used, the Under-Secretary-General for Management shall ensure that the electronic data interchange system is capable of ensuring authentication and confidentiality of the information transmitted.

Advance and progress payments

Rule 105.19

(a) Except where normal commercial practice or the interests of the United Nations so require, no contract or other form of undertaking shall be made on behalf

of the United Nations which requires a payment or payments on account in advance of the delivery of products or the performance of contractual services. Whenever an advance payment is agreed to, the reasons therefor shall be recorded.

(b) In addition to paragraph (a) above and notwithstanding rule 105.2, the Under-Secretary-General for Management may, where necessary, authorize progress payments.

D. Property management

Authority and responsibility

Rule 105.20

The Under-Secretary-General for Management is responsible for the management of the property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets of the United Nations, including all systems governing their receipt, valuation, recording, utilization, safekeeping, maintenance, transfer and disposal, including by sale, and shall designate the officials responsible for performing property management functions.

Rule 105.21

Physical verification shall be carried out and records maintained of property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets of the Organization, in accordance with policies established by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

Review bodies related to property management

Rule 105.22

(a) The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall establish review bodies for Headquarters and other locations to render written advice in respect of loss, damage, impairment or other discrepancy regarding the property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets of the United Nations. The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall establish the composition and terms of reference of such review bodies, which shall include procedures for determining the cause of such loss, damage, impairment or other discrepancy, the disposal action to be taken in accordance with rules 105.23 and 105.24 and the degree of responsibility, if any, attaching to any official of the United Nations or other party for such loss, damage or other discrepancy.

(b) Where the advice of a review body is required, no final action in respect of United Nations property loss, damage, impairment or other discrepancy may be taken before such advice is received. In cases where the Under-Secretary-General for Management decides not to accept the advice of such a body, he or she shall record in writing, the reasons for that decision.

Sale/disposal of property

Rule 105.23

Property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets of the United Nations that are declared surplus, unserviceable or obsolete following a recommendation by a review body shall be disposed of, transferred or sold after competitive bidding, unless the review body:

- (a) Estimates that the sales value is less than an amount to be specified by the Under-Secretary-General for Management;
- (b) Considers that the exchange of property in partial or full payment for replacement equipment or supplies is in the best interest of the Organization;
- (c) Deems it appropriate to transfer surplus property from one project or operation for use in another and determines the fair market value at which the transfer(s) shall be effected;
- (d) Determines that the destruction of the surplus or unserviceable material will be more economical or is required by law or by the nature of the property;
- (e) Determines that the interests of the United Nations will be served through the disposal of the property by gift or by sale at a nominal price to an intergovernmental organization, a Government or governmental agency or some other non-profit organization.

Rule 105.24

Except as provided for in rule 105.23, sales of property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets shall be on commercial terms.

Disposition of assets of peacekeeping operations

Regulation 5.14. Following the liquidation of a peacekeeping operation, equipment and other property shall be disposed of in accordance with the Financial Regulations and Rules and in the manner indicated below:

- (a) Equipment in good condition that conforms to established standardization or is considered compatible with existing equipment will be redeployed to other peacekeeping operations or will be placed in reserve to form start-up kits for use by future missions;**
- (b) Equipment not required for current or future peacekeeping operations may be redeployed to other United Nations activities funded from assessed contributions, provided that there is a demonstrated need for the equipment;**
- (c) Equipment not required for current or future peacekeeping operations or other United Nations activities funded from assessed contributions but which may be useful for the operations of other United Nations agencies, international organizations or non-governmental organizations will be sold to such agencies or organizations;**

(d) Any equipment or property not required or which it is not feasible to dispose of in accordance with subparagraphs (a), (b) or (c) above or which is in poor condition will be subject to commercial disposal in accordance with the procedures applicable to other United Nations equipment or property;

(e) Any assets which have been installed in a country and which, if dismantled, would set back the rehabilitation of that country shall be provided to the duly recognized Government of that country in return for compensation in a form to be agreed by the Organization and the Government. This refers in particular to airfield installations and equipment, buildings, bridges and mine-clearing equipment. Where such assets cannot be disposed of in this manner or otherwise, they will be contributed free of charge to the Government of the country concerned. Such contributions require the prior approval of the General Assembly.

A report on the final disposition of assets for each liquidated peacekeeping operation shall be submitted to the General Assembly.

E. Internal audit

Regulation 5.15. The Office of Internal Oversight Services shall conduct independent internal audits in accordance with regulation 5.8 (d) and in conformity with generally accepted auditing standards. Internal auditors shall review, evaluate and report on the use of financial resources and on the effectiveness, adequacy and application of internal financial control systems, procedures and other relevant internal controls. Internal audits shall also include the following elements:

(a) Compliance of financial transactions with General Assembly resolutions, approved programmes and other legislative mandates, with regulations and rules and related administrative instructions and with the approved recommendations of external oversight bodies;

(b) Economy, efficiency and effectiveness of financial, physical and human resources management and utilization and of programme delivery, including by examining the structure of the Organization and its responsiveness to the requirements of programmes and legislative mandates and by conducting management audits.

Article VI Accounting

Financial statements

Regulation 6.1. The financial statements shall be prepared annually in United States dollars in accordance with the present Regulations and Rules, decisions of the appropriate legislative bodies and the International Public Sector Accounting Standards.

Regulation 6.2. The Secretary-General shall transmit the annual financial statements to the Board of Auditors following certification and no later than three months following the end of the relevant financial period.

Regulation 6.3. Appropriate separate accounts shall be maintained for all trust funds and reserve and special accounts.

Rule 106.1

(a) For all accounts of the United Nations, except for peacekeeping operations with special accounts, annual financial statements for the period ending 31 December shall be submitted to the Board of Auditors no later than 31 March of the following year. Copies of financial statements shall also be transmitted to the Advisory Committee.

(b) In the case of peacekeeping operations with special accounts, annual financial statements for the period ending 30 June shall be submitted to the Board of Auditors no later than 30 September of the same year.

(c) In accordance with the International Public Sector Accounting Standards, financial statements submitted to the Board of Auditors for all accounts shall include:

- (i) A statement of financial performance;
- (ii) A statement of financial position;
- (iii) A statement of changes in net assets;
- (iv) A statement of cash flows;

(v) A statement of comparison of budget and actual amounts, on the basis of the budget; and

(vi) Notes to the financial statements, comprising a summary of significant accounting policies and other explanatory notes.

Authority and responsibility

Rule 106.2

Responsibility for the accounts is assigned to the Under-Secretary-General for Management, who shall establish accounting systems.

Accrual basis accounting

Rule 106.3

Unless otherwise directed by the particular terms governing the operation of a trust fund or special account, all financial transactions shall be recorded in the accounts on an accrual basis in compliance with the International Public Sector Accounting Standards.

Currency of accounting records

Regulation 6.4. The accounts of the Organization shall be presented in United States dollars. Accounting records may, however, be kept in such currency or currencies as the Secretary-General may deem necessary.

Rule 106.4

Transactions may be recorded in both the transaction currency and the United States dollar. The accounts shall be maintained in United States dollars.

Accounting for exchange rate fluctuations

Rule 106.5

(a) The Under-Secretary-General for Management shall establish the operational rates of exchange between the United States dollar and other currencies. The operational rates of exchange shall be used for recording all United Nations transactions.

(b) Receipts and payments in currencies other than the United States dollar shall be recorded on the basis of the operational rate of exchange prevailing on the transaction date. Any difference between the actual amount on exchange and the amount that would have been obtained at the operational rate of exchange shall be accounted for as loss or gain on exchange.

(c) When closing the final accounts for a financial period, any negative balance on the account for "loss or gain on exchange" shall be debited to other expenses, while any positive balance on the account for "loss or gain on exchange" shall be credited to other/miscellaneous revenue.

Accounting for proceeds from the sale of property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets

Rule 106.6

(a) For accounting purposes, any gain from the sale of property, plant and equipment and intangible assets shall be credited to other/miscellaneous revenue and any loss shall be debited to other expenses.

(b) For budgetary purposes, the proceeds from the sale of property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets may be applied against the cost of replacement.

Writing off losses of assets, including cash, receivables, property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets

Regulation 6.5. The Secretary-General may, after full investigation, authorize the writing-off of losses of assets, including cash, inventories and property, plant and equipment, provided that a statement of all such amounts written off shall be submitted to the Board of Auditors with the annual financial statements submitted in accordance with regulation 6.1.

Rule 106.7

(a) The Under-Secretary-General for Management may, after investigation, authorize the writing-off of losses of assets, including cash, receivables, property, plant and equipment, inventories and intangible assets. A summary statement of losses shall be provided to the Board of Auditors not later than three months following the end of the financial period.

(b) The investigation shall in each case fix the responsibility, if any, attaching to any official(s) of the United Nations for the loss or losses. Such official(s) may be required to reimburse the United Nations either partially or in full. Final determination as to all surcharges to be made against staff members or others as the result of losses will be made by the Under-Secretary-General for Management.

Archives

Rule 106.8

Accounting and other financial records and all supporting documents shall be retained for established periods in accordance with policies after which, on approval of the Under-Secretary-General for Management, they may be destroyed.

Article VII Board of Auditors

Appointment of a board of auditors

Regulation 7.1. The General Assembly shall appoint a board of auditors to perform an annual audit of the accounts of the United Nations. This board shall consist of three members, each of whom shall be the Auditor-General (or officer holding the equivalent title) of a Member State.

Tenure of office of the members of the Board of Auditors

Regulation 7.2. The members of the Board of Auditors shall be elected by the General Assembly for a non-renewable term of office of six years' duration. The term of office shall commence on 1 July and expire on 30 June six years subsequent thereto. The term of office of one of the members shall expire every other year. Consequently, the Assembly shall elect every two years a member to take office from 1 July of the following year.

Regulation 7.3. If a member of the Board of Auditors ceases to hold office as Auditor-General (or equivalent title) in his or her own country, the member's tenure of office shall thereupon be terminated and he or she shall be succeeded as a member of the Board by his or her successor as Auditor-General. A Board member may not otherwise be removed during his or her tenure of office except by the General Assembly.

Audit standards, scope and operations

Regulation 7.4. The audit shall be conducted in conformity with generally accepted common auditing standards and, subject to any special directions of the General Assembly, in accordance with the additional terms of reference set out in the annex to the present Regulations.

Regulation 7.5. The Board of Auditors may make observations with respect to the efficiency of the financial procedures, the accounting system, the internal financial controls and, in general, the administration and management of the Organization.

Regulation 7.6. The Board of Auditors shall be completely independent and solely responsible for the conduct of the audit.

Regulation 7.7. The Advisory Committee may request the Board of Auditors to perform certain specific examinations and issue separate reports on the results.

Regulation 7.8. The Board of Auditors shall, subject to the concurrence of the Advisory Committee, allocate and rotate the audit work among the members of the Board.

Facilities

Regulation 7.9. The Secretary-General shall provide the Board of Auditors with the facilities it may require in the performance of the audit.

Regulation 7.10. For the purpose of making a local or special examination or of effecting economies in the audit cost, the Board of Auditors may engage the services of any national Auditor-General (or officer holding the equivalent title) or commercial public auditors of known repute or any other person or firm which, in the opinion of the Board, is technically qualified.

Reporting

Regulation 7.11. The Board of Auditors shall issue a report on the audit of the financial statements and relevant schedules relating to the accounts for the financial period, which shall include such information as the Board deems necessary with regard to matters referred to in regulation 7.5 and in the additional terms of reference.

Regulation 7.12. The reports of the Board of Auditors shall be transmitted to the General Assembly through the Advisory Committee, together with the audited financial statements, in accordance with any directions given by the Assembly. The Advisory Committee shall examine the financial statements and the audit reports and shall forward them to the Assembly with such comments as it deems appropriate.

Annex

Additional terms of reference governing the audit of the United Nations

1. The Board of Auditors shall perform jointly and severally such audit of the accounts of the United Nations, including all trust funds and special accounts, as it deems necessary in order to satisfy itself:

(a) That the financial statements are in accord with the books and records of the Organization;

(b) That, in all material respects, the transactions recorded in the financial statements conform to the authorities that govern them;

(c) That the internal controls, including the internal audit, are adequate in the light of the extent of reliance placed thereupon;

(d) That the accounting policies selected and applied are consistent with the International Public Sector Accounting Standards and are appropriate in the circumstances, and that accounting estimates are reasonable.

2. The Board of Auditors shall be the sole judge as to the acceptance in whole or in part of certifications and representations by the Secretary-General and may proceed to such detailed examination and verification as it chooses of all financial records, including those relating to inventories and property, plant and equipment.

3. The Board of Auditors and its staff shall have free access at all convenient times to all books, records and other documentation which are, in the opinion of the Board, necessary for the performance of the audit. Information which is classified as privileged and which the Secretary-General (or his or her designated senior official) agrees is required by the Board for the purposes of the audit and information classified as confidential shall be made available on application. The Board and its staff shall respect the privileged and confidential nature of any information so classified which has been made available and shall not make use of it except in direct connection with the performance of the audit. The Board may draw the attention of the General Assembly to any denial of information classified as privileged which, in its opinion, was required for the purpose of the audit.

4. The Board of Auditors shall have no power to adjust the financial statements but shall draw to the attention of the Secretary-General, for appropriate action, any transaction concerning which it entertains doubt as to legality or propriety. Audit objections to these or any other transactions arising during the examination of the accounts shall be communicated immediately to the Secretary-General.

5. The Board of Auditors (or such of its officers as it may designate) shall express and sign an opinion on the financial statements of the United Nations. The opinion shall include the following basic elements:

(a) A title, an addressee and identification of the financial statements audited;

(b) A reference to the responsibility of the Secretary-General and the responsibility of the Board of Auditors;

(c) A reference to the audit standards followed;

- (d) A description of the scope of the audit;
 - (e) An expression of opinion on the financial statements as to whether:
 - (i) The financial statements present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Organization as at the end of the period and the results and cash flows for the year then ended; and
 - (ii) The financial statements have been properly prepared in accordance with the International Public Sector Accounting Standards and the Financial Regulations and Rules of the United Nations;
 - (f) An expression of opinion on the compliance of transactions with the Financial Regulations and legislative authority;
 - (g) The date of the opinion;
 - (h) The names and positions of the members of the Board of Auditors;
 - (i) Should it be necessary, a reference to the report of the Board of Auditors on the financial statements.
6. The report of the Board of Auditors to the General Assembly should refer to:
- (a) The type and scope of its examination;
 - (b) Matters affecting the completeness or accuracy of the financial statements, including, where appropriate:
 - (i) Information necessary to the correct interpretation of the accounts;
 - (ii) Any amounts which ought to have been accrued but which have not been brought to account;
 - (iii) Contingencies which have not been properly disclosed in the financial statements;
 - (iv) Expenditures not properly substantiated;
 - (v) Whether proper books of accounts have been kept; where in the presentation of statements there are deviations of a material nature from the stated accounting standards and policies these should be disclosed;
 - (c) Other matters which should be brought to the notice of the General Assembly, such as:
 - (i) Cases of fraud or presumptive fraud;
 - (ii) Wasteful or improper expenditure of the Organization's money or other assets (notwithstanding that the accounting for the transaction may be correct);
 - (iii) Expenditure likely to commit the Organization to further outlay on a large scale;
 - (iv) Any defect in the general system or controls governing receipts and disbursements, or assets, including inventories and property, plant and equipment;
 - (v) Expenditure not in accordance with the intention of the General Assembly after making allowance for duly authorized transfers within the budget;

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- (vi) Expenditure in excess of appropriations as amended by duly authorized transfers within the budget;
- (vii) Expenditure not in conformity with the authority which governs it;
- (d) The accuracy or otherwise of inventories and property, plant and equipment records as determined by stock-taking and examination of the records;
- (e) If appropriate, transactions accounted for in a previous financial period concerning which further information has been obtained or transactions in a later financial period concerning which it seems desirable that the General Assembly should have early knowledge.
7. The Board of Auditors may make such observations with respect to its findings resulting from the audit and such comments on the Secretary-General's financial report as it deems appropriate to the General Assembly or to the Secretary-General.
8. Whenever the scope of audit of the Board of Auditors is restricted, or whenever the Board is unable to obtain sufficient evidence, it shall refer to the matter in its opinion and report, making clear in its report the reasons for its comments and the effect on the financial position and the financial transactions as recorded.
9. In no case shall the Board of Auditors include criticism in its report without first affording the Secretary-General an adequate opportunity of explanation on the matter under observation.
10. The Board is not required to mention any matter referred to in the foregoing that, in its opinion, is insignificant in all respects.
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